

Renewable energy implementation and Industry self-generation: The case of Tunisia

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Executive Summary

Tunisia faces a pressing need to diversify its energy mix and reduce its reliance on electricity and natural gas imports. This study, utilizing the OSeMOSYS modeling tool, explores three future scenarios to assess the future technology needs, investment requirements, and emissions reductions associated with the integration of renewable energy in electricity and industrial sectors.

The findings indicate that, without significant policy changes, the country will continue to rely on fossil fuels, resulting in high emissions. However, meeting Tunisia's renewable energy targets could reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 75% by 2050, though it requires 4 times more investments.

Achieving the target of 30% renewable energy contribution by 2030 is a bold objective that requires a significant shift in a relatively short time frame. Though it could be viable with the right policies in place and the financial collaboration of international organizations. Furthermore, introducing self-generation within the industrial sector, while more costly due to higher prices of off-grid solar systems, can offer additional emissions reductions and greater energy autonomy.

1. Introduction:

In 2015, Tunisia introduced a self-generation policy that allows individuals and organizations to produce electricity from renewable energy sources, primarily for their own consumption. This initiative is especially important for the industrial sector, which accounts for nearly one-third of the country's total energy demand.

The framework supports Tunisia's broader goals of enhancing energy independence and diversifying its energy mix. Currently, about 95% of Tunisia's electricity is generated from natural gas-powered plants, relying on both domestic production and significant imports, while renewable sources contribute only by 5%.

To address this imbalance, several projects are underway to increase the share of renewables to 30% of electricity generation by 2030. This transition is a key component of Tunisia's strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and meet its long-term renewable energy targets.

In this report, 3 scenarios are created based on this context aiming to study the optimal repartition of electricity generation power plants, the associated costs and the impacts in terms of carbon dioxide emissions.

2. Methodology:

The chosen scenarios will be analyzed using the Modelling User Interface for OSeMOSYS (MUIO). OSeMOSYS is a linear optimization model designed to reduce system expenses and ensure energy requirements are met. It supports long-term energy planning and policy analysis by facilitating efficient allocation of resources, technologies, and investments.

Demand growth is assumed to be 5% yearly throughout the modeling period spanning from 2021 to 2025. Expected economic growth, industry modernization programs, and national energy policy goals served as the basis for future assumptions.

The model builds on national energy statistics, industrial electricity consumption data, and the demand growth projection mentioned above to simulate technico-economic evolutions under different policy conditions.

The analysis is based on official government publications, pertinent sector reports, and open access sources from governmental websites. To create a tangible baseline model, the existing electrical sector structure was meticulously calibrated across 2021 to 2023. The model chooses between natural gas, solar (centralized and decentralized) and wind power plants to meet demand needs under the different scenarios hypotheses.

Three scenarios were designed to assess different development paths for the electricity sector:

- Scenario 1: Business-as-Usual (BAU) — Assumes the continuation of existing trends without major policy shifts. Renewable energy projects are integrated as opportunities arise, but there are no explicit emission reduction targets or capacity installation goals.
- Scenario 2: Achievement of Renewable Energy Targets — Models the sector's transition toward national objectives, achieving a 30% renewable share in the electricity mix by 2030 and 80% by 2050. It investigates the impacts on energy infrastructure and technology adoptions required to reach these milestones.
- Scenario 3: Industrial Self-generation of green electricity — Focuses on increased self-generation and consumption of electricity within industrial facilities. This scenario explores how onsite renewable installations (mainly solar) contribute to reducing the industry's grid dependency and lowering overall sectoral emissions.

The results provide a comparative perspective on the potential strategies available to decarbonize Tunisia's industrial sector while supporting economic growth.

3. Results:

The OSeMOSYS model is based on the Reference Energy System presented below:

Figure : OSeMOSYS model Reference Energy System for Tunisia

The Reference Energy System (RES) illustrates the structure and flow of Tunisia's energy system, from resource supply to final consumption. It takes into account the primary energy supplies, notably natural gas mining and imports, and renewable energies such as solar and wind, which feed into corresponding technologies like natural gas power plants, solar PV and wind turbines.

The generated electricity is then transmitted and distributed through the grid.

A distinctive feature is the inclusion of solar self-generation, representing decentralized production, particularly relevant for industries or isolated users. The final energy is consumed across sectors reflecting national demand coverage.

In this study, we will focus on the evolution of production by each power plant, the allocated capacity for each technology, relative investment costs, and final CO₂ emissions.

The results are as follows:

Figure 1: Production by technology

Figure 2: Accumulated new capacity

Figure 3: Annualized Investment Cost

In the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, electricity production remains heavily dependent on natural gas power plants (95,5% in 2050), with only minor contributions from solar and wind technologies and fixed levels of electricity imports. A similar trend is observed in terms of cumulative new capacity additions.

In contrast, the second scenario, which aligns with the renewable energy targets outlined in Tunisia's national energy strategy, shows a significant increase in solar power generation and overall investment starting in 2030, followed by a rise in wind energy capacity beginning in 2042. This shift reflects the gradual replacement of fossil fuel-based generation. The delayed uptake of wind energy is partly due to how the model accounts for residual wind turbine capacity. Moreover, although OSeMOSYS does not explicitly model barriers such as administrative hurdles or land availability, these limitations can be indirectly reflected through delayed or forced technology deployment in the model. For instance, while Tunisia relies on both wind and solar, the model initially chooses wind as the most cost-effective technology over solar in the second scenario, so a minimal limit of 0.240 GW for solar capacity had to be imposed in the first few years up to 2025 in order to simulate reality and get the results shown above.

The third scenario introduces electricity self-generation within the industrial sector. Industries, particularly those engaged in exports, are increasingly investing in solar technologies to reduce their carbon footprint and avoid the potential financial burden of carbon taxes. As a result, the deployment of off-grid solar panels gradually increases. While this does not directly reduce the cumulative installed capacity of natural gas power plants, it does affect electricity production patterns: the system becomes less reliant on

natural gas and centralized solar generation, instead shifting toward increased investment and production in wind energy.

Figure 4 : Emissions

When comparing all three scenarios in terms of carbon emissions, both scenarios 2 and 3 achieve nearly a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2050 relative to the BAU scenario. Scenario 3 goes even further, achieving slightly deeper emission cuts (-2 Mtons) as a consequence of the integration of self-generation in the industrial sector, which is typically among the most emissions-intensive sectors of the economy.

5. Discussion:

The Tunisian electricity sector currently depends mainly on three energy sources: natural gas, solar, and wind. As of 2025, fossil fuel-based power plants supply approximately 95% of the country’s electricity, while renewables contribute by only 5%. These figures serve as the foundation for the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario. With no major constraints, the model projects a continued reliance on natural gas. This leads to relatively low investment requirements, with cumulative costs remaining below 1,400 million USD by 2050.

In contrast, Scenario 2 reflects Tunisia's ambition to increase the share of renewable energy by 30% in 2030, 50% in 2040, and 80% in 2050. Achieving these targets entails a significant rise in installed capacity, meaning the country would need to double the existing capacity for solar starting 2027 and reach around 24 GW of solar installed capacity and 17 GW in wind by 2050. Which also translates to investment—totaling an accumulated 55000 million USD across the modeling period—primarily directed toward solar and wind infrastructure. However, this investment leads to a major reduction in fossil fuel

dependency and a corresponding 75% decrease in CO₂ emissions compared to the BAU scenario. The long-term environmental benefits suggest a compelling case for prioritizing renewable energy in national planning.

Scenario 3 explores the integration of electricity self-generation in the industrial sector. This scenario not only shows increased deployment of off-grid solar systems (meeting 30% of the industry's needs) but also a greater share of wind energy in the generation mix, which together result in an additional 500M.USD in investment costs in 2050 compared to Scenario 2. These higher costs stem from the relatively expensive nature of decentralized solar technologies.

From an environmental perspective, both Scenarios 2 and 3 cut emissions by three quarters in 2050 compared to BAU. Scenario 3 delivers slightly deeper emissions reductions (minus 2 million tons yearly since 2030), underlining the potential of industrial self-generation to make a significant contribution to decarbonization efforts.

These findings have clear policy implications:

Even though, in the second scenario, a jump in renewable energy integration rates from 5% to 30% within a 5-year timeframe seems too ambitious, it is possible with financial contributions from international organisations to meet the budget demands.

For Scenario 3, by producing and consuming their own green electricity, industries can better manage future carbon tax liabilities while delivering faster on national energy objectives and CO₂ emission targets. Government support through targeted subsidies, carbon pricing mechanisms and tax incentives could encourage greater self-generation in the industrial sector. This support can also make way for a private-public collaboration where the private sector would take on most of the expenses but still benefit from governmental incentives and advantages.

One challenge highlighted by the study is the modeling of existing non-technical barriers (such as permitting delays) as delays in technology uptake. This obstacle particularly concerns wind deployment in Scenario 2. These real life delays were simulated as a restriction on wind technology investments for a number of years. As a result, the model did not implement wind capacities and kept wind energy integration on hold until 2042.

Alternatively, an opportunity lies in further exploring the economic viability of self-generation. Additional work on scenario 3 could potentially explore fluctuations in financial parameters—such as falling PV costs or increasing fossil fuel taxes— which might accelerate the adoption of off-grid solar technologies. Understanding these thresholds would help inform policies that aim to make renewables not just a strategic choice, but the economically optimal one. Additionally, the study's focus on the industrial

sector could be further expanded in future research to include the residential and transport sectors, which also contribute significantly to national emissions.

7. Conclusion:

Continuing the current trends without imposing any policy shifts might be less expensive in terms of costs and investments, however it won't contribute positively in terms of clean energy production, as emissions will reach 42 million tons of CO₂ in 2050, cutting on imports of electricity and natural gas and decreasing carbon emissions in the long run.

As energy demand is increasingly on the rise and industries are more hungry for electricity, it is necessary to add renewable energies to the arsenal of energy production, approximately adding 5 times the current installed capacity for renewables by 2030 and halving the dependence on natural gas, without limiting it to the burden of importing fossil fuels and electricity, to invest more in renewables that adapt to the country's climate.

To turn these insights into action soon, Tunisia should prioritize renewable energy integration in national planning and encourage energy-intensive sectors to commit to the energy transition, as targeted government support—such as subsidies or carbon pricing—could incentivize industrial self-generation, enabling cost-sharing with the private sector while advancing national climate goals.

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